

Models for the integration of phenotypic and genomic data with precision prognostic purposes

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Enhanced analysis and validation performances with multiple dataset to annotate cell type

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Abstract:

This report is based on the previous one presented in June 2020 [1] and contains the results of an extensive evaluation of the previously proposed methodology for the identification of cell types throughout various public datasets of the most diverse nature, which now include cells from human in addition to mouse. Furthermore, the model has been improved in such a way that it is now capable of detecting when a cell has a different sub-type from those that have been used during the learning phase.

1 Datasets

The network architecture was evaluated in two different scenarios: 1) the performance of the proposed method for the identification of cell types, and 2) novelty detection task providing a measure to unknown cell types during the learning process. We used three scRNA-seq datasets belong to two organisms, human and mouse, and all of them are publicly available. They are downloaded from NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) [2] database project webpage.

The performance of cell type identification was evaluated with three datasets. And the cell type annotation analysis was performing with melanoma dataset.

1.1 Human scRNA-seq datasets

Two of the human scRNA-seq datasets has been downloaded via scibet webpage [3].

The first data set is the fresh peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) dataset. We use the exact dataset after random down-sampling provided by scibet webpage, where all cell types have an equal proportion of 2500 samples for each 7 cell type. Furthermore, it has more than 15000 genes (see *Table 1*).

The second dataset called melanoma is also a processed version, we use the exact *training* and *testing* datasets which are downloaded from the scibet webpage separately. These datasets have more than 17000

genes. The training dataset profiles 5 cell types for 2761 samples, the testing dataset profiles 6 cell types for 3412 samples (see *Table 2*).

1.2 Mouse scRNA-seq dataset

The mouse dataset is the combination of 33 datasets ([4]) from different experiments and laboratories and they are downloaded from NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) [2]. It profiles 9 cell types for 13645 samples with more than 9000 genes.(see *Table 3*).

Table 1: PBMC dataset

Cell type	# of samples
CD14	2500
CD19	2500
CD34	2500
CD56	2500
Cyt	2500
Memory	2500
Treg	2500

Table 2: melanoma dataset

Cell type	# of samples	
	<i>training</i>	<i>testing</i>
B.cell	573	245
Macrophage	294	126
NK	64	28
T.CD4	599	257
T.CD8	1231	528
Neg.cell	-	2228

Table 3: Mouse dataset

Cell type	# of samples
ESC	9123
neuron	3667
spleen	420
HSC	202
2cell	85
4cell	55
8cell	53
ICM	22
zygote	18

2 Methods

2.1 Biological Knowledge Integration

In this work, we propose a pathway-based neural network that uses the signalling networks found in the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) repository [5] as priors to impose constrains in how the model is built, with the aim to reduce the size of the network (by increasing the sparsity of the weights) while providing a more interpretable network from a biological point of view, following the works of [6, 7]. In brief, the pathway priors implementation can be summarised in the following steps: 1) each pathway was considered as a biological unit and it was represented by one node of the first inner layer in the architecture, and 2) a gene from the input layer is only connected to those nodes that represent pathways that contain the given gene, we fix the weight that connects to other pathways to 0, while the remaining weights are initialised using traditional techniques, see Figure 1 for a visual representation of the process. For a more comprehensive information of how the proposed model works see [8, 1].

Figure 1: Biological information integration

Although the neural network is trained using a supervised approach, the features learned by the intermediate layers can be used to encode any given cell into a reduced space that contains the essential information about the cell type. The encoding is extracted by detaching the output (*soft-max*) layer during the inference/prediction and computing the activation values of the last hidden layer, see Figure 2 for a visual representation of the encoding capabilities of the pathway-informed neural network with one and two hidden layer designs.

Figure 2: Encoding information of the network

2.2 Cell Type Annotation

One of the problems of many supervised algorithms for cell-type annotation (and other classification tasks) [3] consists of the inability to distinguish when new cell types are present in any given set of predicted samples. Although the proposed pathway-informed neural network can carry out unsupervised analyses, which can be used to showcase similarities between groups, the problem persists if the clustered cells should be annotated. This phenomenon is partially related to the overconfidence of supervised NNs [9, 10]: in simple terms, the model is unable to produce a set of lower than normal probabilities for every class, thus a decision is always taken with a high confidence.

To overcome such problems we have enhanced the pathway-informed neural network with the ability to identify if a previously unseen cell belongs to the known cell types (those used during the model training) or not. Once a cell has been categorized as known, we proceed to use the supervised capabilities of our model in order to annotate it. And, on the contrary, cells categorized as unknown are labeled as such and further inspection could be carried out by using the unsupervised capabilities of the network.

This identification of unknown cell types can be summarised as:

1. Split the training data into two complementary sets, referred as *learning* and *validation*.
2. The model (as usual) is fitted to the *learning* set using the methods motioned before.
3. The training set is encoded using the trained network.
4. A Local Outlier Factor (LOF) model [11] is fitted to the encoded representation of the *learning* set and used to predict the LOF scores.
5. A decision boundary for the LOF scores is set using the *validation* set. Thus, we overcome the overconfidence of the NN when encoding samples by setting the threshold for detecting anomalies with a holdout set.
6. A new sample is first encoded using the learned representation by the pathway-informed neural network, then scored using the LOF model, and assigned an "unknown" label if the LOF threshold is met. In other case it is labeled according to the predicted probabilities given by the NN.

The Local Outlier Factor (LOF) algorithm is an unsupervised outlier detection method that is not specially designed for high dimensional spaces, however thanks to the reduced dimension of the encoding we can overcome such difficulties. This technique mimics the random projection methods used in the high dimensional adaption of the LOF algorithm [12]. The algorithm tries to find by means of k-neighbors-based routines the difference of densities between any given point and its neighbors: a high density point has its neighbors at short distances from it, whereas a low density point has its neighbors very close between them but not to the original point.

2.3 Architectures, parameters and hyperparameter selection

The proposed networks were implemented using the Keras API of Tensorflow [13] and the integration of biological nodes are defined over the weight values of the first hidden layer during the initialization step.

The models were trained using stochastic gradient descent (SGD) for mouse analysis and the Adam optimizer for human analysis, using Glorot initialization [14] and 100 training epochs with a mini-batch size of 10.

In addition, we tested several activation functions (tanh, relu, linear and sigmoid) and preprocessing steps (normalization, log-transform and [-1, 1]-scaling). On the one hand, normalization and tanh are the better options for the mouse experiment, which is congruent with the findings of [4]. On the other hand, for both human datasets, we found that the activation function relu is worked better than other approaches. We applied logarithmic preprocessing for the human melanoma dataset and used the same version of the human PBMC dataset as shared in scibet webpage.

Detailed information about the number of nodes of the network and the hyperparameter definition of each architecture is shown in Table 4 in Table 5, respectively.

Organism	Architecture	# of Layer 1	# of Layer 2
mouse	Network with signaling pathway	92^{pbk}	X 100^d
human	Network with signaling pathway	93^{pbk}	X 100^d

Table 4: The details of input, hidden layer and parameters for each architecture. d: dense or fully connected nodes, pbk: prior biological knowledge, X: without second hidden layer

Parameter name	Experiment	Parameter value
epochs	Human & Mouse	100
batch_size	Human & Mouse	10
kernel_initializer	Human & Mouse	glorot_uniform
bias_initializer	Human & Mouse	zeros
activation	Mouse	tanh (hidden layer) / softmax (last layer)
optimizer	Mouse	SGD
activation	Human	relu (hidden layer) / softmax (last layer)
optimizer	Human	Adam

Table 5: Network hyperparameters

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

To analyse the performance of our approach with respect to the cell-type classification task we applied a 50 times repeated cell-type stratified 10-fold cross-validation i.e., it performed 500 iterations splitting the dataset into 10 non-intersecting subsets of samples that maintain the original distribution of the labels. We reported the distribution across the test folds of five well-known classification metrics that summarise the behaviour of the model for the task. Namely, accuracy, balanced accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score. In order to better understand each metric we present the associated formulas with respect to the binary confusion matrix schema (see Table 6).

2.4.1 Accuracy Score

The accuracy is the fraction of correct predictions among the total number of classes [15, 16]:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TruePositive + TrueNegative}{TruePositive + TrueNegative + FalsePositive + FalseNegative}$$

2.4.2 Balanced Accuracy Score

The balanced accuracy is another well-known metric both in binary and in multi-class classification. This metric addresses the issue with unbalanced classes because the accuracy score might mislead when the classes are unbalanced [17]. The formula is [17] :

$$Recall(Sensitivity) = \frac{TruePositive}{TruePositive + FalseNegative}$$

		PREDICTED	
		Positive	Negative
ACTUAL	Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
	Negative	False Positive (FP)	True Negative (TN)

Table 6: Confusion matrix

$$Specificity = \frac{TrueNegative}{TrueNegative + FalsePositive}$$

$$BalancedAccuracy = \frac{Sensitivity + Specificity}{2}$$

2.4.3 Precision Score

Precision is another useful metric to measure the success of prediction when the classes are unbalanced. It shows how the result is relevant with the fraction of true positive elements divided by the total number of positively predicted units [16].

$$Precision = \frac{TruePositive}{TruePositive + FalsePositive}$$

2.4.4 Recall Score

The recall is also useful metric as precision in the case of unbalanced data. It measures the percentage of total relevant results correctly classified [16].

$$Recall = \frac{TruePositive}{TruePositive + FalseNegative}$$

2.4.5 F1 Score

The F1 shows the accuracy by calculating the harmonic mean of precision and recall [16].

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

3 Result

3.1 Cell Type Classification Performance

In this section, the predictive performance measures are shown reporting the predictions against the ground truth. The analysis was conducted following repeated stratified k-fold cross-validation [18] with k=10 and 50 times, i.e., it performed 500 iterations splitting the dataset into 10 subsets 50 times. We evaluated the performance of our approach using five well-known classification metrics based on confusion matrix: accuracy, balanced accuracy, precision, recall and F1 scores (more details in *Evaluation Metrics* section). Finally, we report the average confusion matrix of 500 iterations.

Here, several experiments are reported using three different datasets: mouse, melanoma and PBMC dataset. The aim of using these three datasets is to analyse the network performance beyond several organisms and using balance vs unbalance dataset. The performance of our approach is analysed reporting the performance metrics for each NN design and for each cell type (see *Figure 3* and *Figure 4*), together with the average confusion matrix (see *Figure 5*).

In *Figure 3* and *Figure 4*, the performance metrics are reported for each NN design and for each cell type. In general, the NN designs is performing well without regard to the organism. In *Figure 3*, we can observe good and similar results using the balanced or unbalanced dataset. Furthermore, the performance of each cell type is rely on the sample size of each cell type, i.e., the size of the samples is important during the prediction as we can see in *Figure 4*.

Finally, the confusion matrices are shown in *Figure 5* for three dataset. In *Figure 5a* and *5b*, we can observe the heatmap of the confusion matrix on the PBMC dataset and it can be observed a high

Figure 3: Network performance

discriminating power in almost all cell types. The proposed method could still provide a high discriminating power as can be observed between Figure 5c - 5f, with better results whether the cell types have a high number of samples (see Table 2 and Table 3).

3.2 Cell Type Annotation with Novelty Detection

In order to check the performance of our unknown cell-type identification enhancements, we have used the same (*Melanoma*) dataset and splits as in [3], where an state of the art algorithm is used for the same purpose. The training set is comprised of B cells, Macrophage, NK and T.CD4/8, whereas the test contains cells belonging to the previous types and Negative Cells: a mix of malignant cells, CAF cells and endothelial cells (see Table 2).

The task consists in fitting a model using the *training* set and then evaluating its capability to correctly annotate the Negative Cells as unknown, while still providing accurate labels for the known cell types.

In Figure 6 we show the distribution of the similarity (abnormality) score for the *melanoma* dataset. In the left graph, we can see the distribution of the scores across all the known cell types for the training *training* with the threshold (the horizontal line) computed as outlined in the Methods section. Instead, in the right graph we observe the distribution of the score across the cell types belonging to the *testing* split, the superposing of the previously computed threshold. The superposition of the previously computed

Figure 4: The metric details for each cell type

threshold allows us to observe the ability of the method to classify the vast majority of Negative Cells as *unseen/unknown* (outliers), while almost all the remaining cells are found on the other side of the border. As we can see, the results are outstanding and comparable, with a better diagonal, than those found in [3]. A more fine-grained visualization of the performance over the test can be obtained by inspecting the resulting confusion matrix (see Figure 7). Additionally, in Figure 8 we provide a 2D visual representation of the encoded representation of both splits.

3.3 Functional Analysis in Melanoma Dataset

As we have said before, one of the main benefits of knowledge-informed neural networks is the ability to process the learned representation through the *biological* nodes in order to extract knowledge about the samples where the inference is performed. In our case we have nodes that represent signaling pathways that by means of their activation values we can use to understand the functionalities associated to the predicted cell types.

In our preprint [8], we extracted the 10 most relevant *pathway-nodes* for each of the cell types studied in the *Melanoma* dataset. The main results are in agreement with the literature, which could be a good indicator that a closer inspection of the model can guide future investigations. For example, here we provide one of such interpretations as extracted from our preprint (under blind review at the time of writing this report):

(a) PBMC dataset - 1 layer design

(b) PBMC dataset - 2 layer design

(c) melanoma dataset - 1 layer design

(d) melanoma dataset - 2 layer design

(e) mouse dataset - 1 layer design

(f) mouse dataset - 2 layer design

Figure 5: Average confusion matrix

Figure 6: Similarity score - Melanoma dataset

Figure 7: The final confusion matrix for melanoma dataset

Figure 8: Encoding visualization for melanoma dataset - *training* and *testing*

B cells mediate the production of antigen-specific immunoglobulin (Ig) against pathogens. The most important pathways for B cell functioning would be those engaged in cell-to-cell communication, proliferation, protein expression, and secretion. The pathways that appear among the 10 most relevant only for B-cells are: *Aldosterone-regulated sodium reabsorption* (hsa04960), *Pancreatic secretion* (hsa04972), *Complement and coagulation cascades* (hsa04610) and *Ovarian steroidogenesis* (hsa04913). *Complement and coagulation cascades* (hsa04610) consist of a nonspecific defense mechanism against pathogens. Although the complement system works in the innate immunity, complement effectors are engaged with humoral immunity at multiple stages of B-cell differentiation and can influence B-cell biology on several levels through the complement receptors that they express [19, 20]. The rest are pathways mainly involved in the secretion of substances and ion flow through the cellular membranes. It is expected in B cells that modules engaged in secretion processes are active, given that they expand their secretory organelles in their differentiation process [21].

4 Discussion and Future Work

In this report, an extensive evaluation of the previous pathway-informed neural network methodology for the identification of cell types is shown. We used several datasets from several organisms and balanced vs unbalanced datasets. Furthermore, we provided as an improvement a measure to identify unknown new cell types using the Local Outlier Factor method over the learned representations of the NN. We have enhanced our method with the ability to identify if a previously unseen cell belongs to the known cell (during the training model) types or not.

During this work, we observed that the proposed network is performing well with different datasets and organisms. However, to improve the performance, we might need to have a more complex design. The purpose of this version of proposed network is to verify that our concept has practical potential while improving the interpretability.

As part of the future work our main goal is to increase the biological complexity of the network by integrating the pathways and signal transduction circuits, while improving the LOF score threshold computation.

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